

CYBERBULLYING DETECTION FROM BANGLA TEXTS EXTRACTED IN SOCIAL MEDIA IMAGES USING MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

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Abstract

As the number of people using social media grows, so does the rate of cyberbullying in Bangladesh. Cyberbullying can take several forms, one of which is text in images. To address this problem, we conducted research in which we utilized OCR to extract text from photos and then used NLP and Machine Learning to detect the existence of Cyberbullying in those texts. 1003 images were gathered from Facebook, and textual data was extracted using OCR. The texts were then preprocessed, and features were extracted before being fed through four Machine Learning algorithms to train. Accuracy, precision, recall, f1-score, training and prediction time, and roc area were all included in the final performance analysis. Finally, the decision Tree algorithm had the highest accuracy of 94% for the test data. Linear SVC (94%), Random Forest (90%), and KNN (88%) came in second, third, and fourth, respectively.

Keywords: Cyberbullying, OCR, Machine Learning, Image, Social Media.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the emergence of technology and internet, there has been a significant impact on social network systems, and relationships have been re-explored all over again. Teenagers spend a fair amount of time online and on different social platforms. Despite the advantages it may provide, their online presence exposes kids to threats and social misbehaviors such as cyberbullying [1].

In July 2021, almost 4.48 billion people were using social media worldwide [2]. Between 2020 and 2021, the number of internet users in our country climbed by 7.7 million. Between 2020 and 2021, more than 9 million users joined social media in Bangladesh, according to a study [3].

According to The Digital Research, a report issued in February by We Are Social, the overall number of social media users in the country is 45 million. The number of people who use social media in Bangladesh is similar to 27.2 percent of the overall population [3].

Bengali is the world's seventh most spoken language, with 228 million native speakers [3], and this number is continually increasing. Furthermore, because Bengali is the national language of Bangladesh and a key language in many parts of India, the number of Bengali social media users has expanded.

However, social media platform preferences differ from country to country. Facebook is still the most popular social media network on the planet. However, six social media networks today each have over one billion monthly active users [2].

People use Facebook to post a variety of statuses, comments, graphics, and other items that are instantaneously available for others to reply to. There are some posts which contain images with text data. Sometimes those images contain bullying or some offensive content which could be hurtful for some peoples.

Cyberbullying must be examined from a variety of angles. Unlike traditional bullying, cyberbullying's methods and approaches evolve over time, making it more destructive and difficult to identify.

There are a number of instruments that can be used to alert authorities to a bullying incidence, as well as groups that attempt to assist victims. But the problem is still far from over and requires a concrete solution.

The most common kind of cyberbullying is text-based cyberbullying. Furthermore, various types are frequently used in conjunction with bullying text. Natural Language Processing (NLP), which requires an annotated corpus to transmit information pertaining to numerous applications, including abusive comment detection [4], involves extracting significant aspects from textual material using computational techniques.

The majority of detection techniques rely on supervised machine learning classifiers. Our cyberbullying detection methods also based on supervised machine learning. In this research, we made following contributions:

- We collected text images from Facebook and extract texts from images using Online character Recognition (OCR), then stored text data into a csv file.
- We presented a comparative analysis among several Machine Learning algorithms and found out that Decision Tree performed best with 94% accuracy and 75% f1-score.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses relevant works, whereas Section 3 discusses our technique. In section 4, we analyze the accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score results and performance of our model. The paper is finally brought to a close in Section 5.

II. RELATED WORKS

Cyberbullying should be detected and stopped, so that adolescents have a safe time while using internet. To detect and prevent cyberbullying many Researchers are working hard and there are some good work also.

There are a variety of ways that suggest systems that can accurately detect cyberbullying. There are some related works about cyberbullying detection are discussed below.

The first is author John Hani et al., who suggested a model based on a labeled Kaggle dataset [5], they used Tf-Idf, sentiment analysis and n-gram features. They classified their featured data using SVM and NN.

The classifiers were evaluated on 2-gram, 3-gram and 4-gram models and categorized into two classes, cyberbullying and non-cyberbullying. The result showed 92.8% accuracy with NN with 3-gram model and 90.3% accuracy for SVM with 4-gram model.

The average f-score for NN is 91.9 percent, whereas SVM is 89.8 percent, indicating that the dataset performed better with NN than SVM. Disadvantage is, their dataset was small, and hence deep learning techniques are proven to outperform machine learning techniques over larger dataset, the result might differ with a large dataset.

Haider et al. proposed multilingual cyberbullying detection techniques by surveying previous works and proposed a plan for Arabic cyberbullying detection [6]. They discussed about many works, where different types of classifiers like NB, SVM, KNN, Decision Tree etc. were used but in most of the case, SVM performed better and the second highest performer was NB. Due to complexity, they don't have many corpus in Arabic language.

They were planning to build their dataset by scrapping comments from OSN platforms. They proposed an approach using NLP and ML, which will efficiently detect cyberbullying. They proposed to classify their data using ML techniques from WEKA toolkit and will measure the results using Recall, Precision and F-measure. Up to the tome of writing this paper, they couldn't find any paper research dealing with Cyberbullying detection in Arabic that is why they perform this survey.

To recognize offensive content, Gulzar et al. presented a root level approach [7]. Data is gathered from Facebook and carefully labeled. They used unigram, bigram, and trigram features in their suggested algorithm, which is divided into two parts: training and testing.

Correct abusive, incorrect abusive, correct not abusive, and wrong not abusive are the four categories in which they categorize their data. The flaw in their research is that they used a root level technique, which is no longer applicable.

Abdullah-Al-Mamun et al. developed a Java program to extract social media data from Facebook and Twitter [8]. Data was manually labeled in two classes, bullied and non-bullied. They used TF-IDF, stemming, tokenization and tri-gram model.

The training and testing was carried into two phrases: including only text-based features, and including both text based features and user information. They have used NB, SVM, J48 and KNN classifiers in WEKA and SVM performed better for with an accuracy of 97%. But their dataset has high-dimensional input space, few irrelevant features.

In another work, Haider et al. tried to achieve that cyberbullying in Arabic language is detectable by using Machine Learning [9]. They collected both Arabic and English data from Facebook and Twitter using Web Scrapping.

Datasets were manually labeled into two classes, bullied and not bullied. They used Tweet to Senti Strength Feature Vector filter, and they trained their dataset using NB and SVM where SVM showed better result in terms of F-measure.

Julinda et al. used a technique that can recognize, localize, and extract horizontally aligned text of various sizes automatically [10]. They devised a method for locating and extracting text from photographs.

The method was enhanced with a local thresholding strategy, which resulted in a significant performance boost. The approach should be extended to include video sequences, and the system should be extended with OCR to check the recognition rate of proposed work, according to the restrictions of their work.

Nisha et al. worked with Optical Character Recognition with the help of Tesseract OCR Engine [11]. Tesseract OCR engine uses LSTM which is a part of Recurrent Neural Network, and it significantly reduces the errors. In this paper, they also discussed about various existing methods of OCR.

Shrinath Janvalkar et al. discussed about the text recognition from an image using OCR [12]. They discussed about the different process that are involved in character recognition process and applications of OCR. The result of their process was not that good.

Ravina et al. also works with the process of Optical Character Recognition [13]. They combined the functionality of OCR and speech synthesizer. The OCR takes an image as input, extracts text from it, and turns it to speech. The limitation is output of the system is often quite noisy and incorrect.

Ahmed P. et al. put Google Docs OCR, Tesseract, ABBY FineReader, and Transym to the test [14]. They used 1227 photos from 15 distinct categories to test the accuracy, reliability, and performance of these OCR tools in their article.

They also looked at OCR software for healthcare informatics. The results revealed that Google Docs OCR and ABBY FineReader performed better. They may have worked with large-scale datasets and applied advanced picture processing.

Noman et al. proposed a summarization of the research that are done in field of OCR and an overview of different aspects of OCR [15]. Acquisition, pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, classification, and post-processing are all covered in this section.

They also proposed to use a combination of these techniques to develop an efficient OCR system as future work. They also described that multilingual character recognition system is still needs to improve.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research aims to detect cyberbullying from text image. Figure 1 shows the methodology.

Figure 1: Proposed Methodology

A. Dataset

For this experiment, we manually collected our image data from Facebook pages. We collected 1003 images in total. Then we manually extracted text data from those images using OCR. Then we stored our text data into a csv file. After that, our dataset was carefully labeled into two categories: offensive and non-offensive.

B. Preprocessing

The majority of social media information is unstructured and does not adhere to any predefined guidelines. These situations are particularly challenging for abusive and slang comments, since people communicate their rage and depression through purposeful misspellings and monotonous repetition of nearby characters.

Several preparation operations are performed in each manual text processing strategy to clear the noisy data. However, due to the nature of abusive remarks, we simply remove special characters and emoticons, as they do not transmit as much information as

offensive comments do. As a result, we manually eliminated some special characters and emoticons during preparation. Null values are also checked.

C. Feature extraction

The textual input is translated into a format that can be fed into machine learning algorithms in this step. To extract the characteristics, we employed TF-IDF (Term Frequency and Inverse Document Frequency). It works with text to determine the weights of words in relation to the document or phrase so that numerical data may be fed to machine learning algorithms [16].

TF-IDF is a statistical measure that evaluates how relevant a word is to a document in a collection of documents. This is done by two metrics:

How many times a word appears in a document

The inverse document frequency of the word across a set of documents. The formula that is used to compute the TF-IDF for a term t of a document d in a document set is,

$$tf-idf(t)=tf(t,d)\times idf(t)$$

This formula has the important effect that when we have a high term frequency (tf) in a given document and a low document frequency of the term in the entire document set, we get a high weight of the tf-idf computation [17].

D. Splitting the dataset into train and test sets

The feature sets obtained from feature selection are divided into 75:25 training and testing sets. A training set is a collection of data that may be used to discover potentially predictive associations. A test set is a collection of data used to assess a prediction relationship's robustness and utility. After train test split, we got:

Table 1: Number of data before and after train test split

Number of rows in the total dataset Before train test split	1003
Number of rows in the training set	752
Number of rows in the test set	251

Table 1 shows the number of data before and after train test split. The models were trained with training sets and then tested with testing sets.

E. Machine Learning Classifiers

Machine learning classifiers are widely used for categorical data. There are various Machine Learning classifiers, but we used four in our research, Linear SVC, Decision Tree, Random Forest and KNN.

a) Linear SVC

SVC (Support Vector Classifier) is a prominent machine learning technique that is also supervised learning. It is used to fit the data provided, and it generates a 'best fit' hyperplane that divides and categorizes the data based on the training data. Different

kernels are used by SV classifiers to create an ideal hyperplane. After obtaining the hyperplane, the model can be given some features to the classifier in order to determine the anticipated class. This supports multiclass, which is handled according to a one-vs.-the-rest scheme. We used Linear SVC, and linear kernel often performs better when the dataset is linearly separable.

b) Decision Tree

A supervised learning method is the Decision Tree. The Decision Tree is frequently employed when dealing with classification challenges. It's a tree-structured classifier with core nodes that provide dataset features, branches that reflect decision rules, and leaf nodes that indicate the result [18].

c) Random Forest

The Random Forest classifier is made up of a number of different decision Trees. Assuming there are T numbers of decision trees generated by the classifier, a random vector v_T is generated for every decision tree, which is also unique in comparison to all the past vectors v_1, \dots, v_{T-1} . All the generated vectors have the same distribution. Then using v_T and the training dataset, a decision tree is grown that generates a classifier $c(i, v_T)$, where i is the input class. When Random Forest completes growing T number of decision trees cast a vote to decide the most efficient input class i . The input class with the most votes become the final choice for classification by Random Forest. Random Forest has methods to overcome the common problem of class imbalance [19].

d) K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)

A basic estimator that uses the distance between data instances to map a given instance to its closest distance neighbor, hence estimating the instance's class.

Under the algorithm of k-NN, an instance is classified according to the class which most of its k nearest neighbors belong to. Since k-NN decides the classes of instances according to a limited number of their neighbors rather than which class domain they are in, it would perform well when the class domains overlap with each other. While we don't have any reference on the class domains, k-NN help us understand the distribution of data set [20].

F. Performance Analysis

We tested our models using the testing datasets and evaluated their performance when we finished training them. We looked at how well our models performed in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

a) Accuracy

Accuracy is the simplest performance metrics of all performance metrics. It is a measure of how accurate our model is. It goes by following equation,

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + FN}{TP + FN + FP + TN}$$

b) Precision

It is the ratio of true positives and total positive predictions. It goes by following equation,

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

c) Recall

It is mainly True Positive Rate (TPR), which tells us about out of all the positive points how many were predicted positive. It goes by following equation,

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

d) F-Measure

It is basically the harmonic mean of precision and recall. Here, we select $\beta=1$, when both FN and FP are important. It goes by following equation,

$$\text{F1 - score} = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We'll talk about the outcome of our dataset. This section goes over the accuracy results in detail. For all four classifiers, Table 2 illustrates the precision, recall, and f1-score of our train data.

Table 2: Precision, Recall and F1-score of Train data

Algorithm	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Decision Tree	1.00	1.00	1.00
Linear SVC	1.00	0.99	1.00
KNN	0.80	0.53	0.64
Random Forest	1.00	0.92	0.99

Table 2 shows that, for our training data, the Decision Tree algorithm achieves 100% precision, recall and f1-score. Then, for Linear SVC we got 99% recall, 100% precision and f1-score. For KNN, we got precision of 80%, Recall of 53% and f1-score of 64%. Then, for Random Forest classifier, we got 100% precision, 92% recall and 99% f1-score, as it shows that Decision Tree showed better result in terms of all three-performance metrics for our training data. Table 3 shows the precision, recall and F1-scores of testing data.

Table 3: Precision, Recall and F1-score of Test data

Algorithm	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Decision Tree	0.73	0.77	0.75
Linear SVC	0.8	0.52	0.63
KNN	0.54	0.42	0.47
Random Forest	1.00	0.16	0.28

As it shows in Table 3, for Decision Tree, we got 73% precision, 80% for Linear SVC, 54% for KNN and 100% for Radom Forest. Random forest outperformed other algorithms in terms of precision. Then we got 77% recall for Decision tree, 52% for Linear SVC, 42% for KNN and 16% for Random forest. We can see, Decision has the highest recall. Then, f1-score, which is an important metrics, we got 75% f1-score for Decision Tree, 63% for Linear SVC, 47% for KNN and 28% for Random forest classifier. As we can see, in terms of f1-score, Decision Tree performed better. Figure 2 shows the accuracy scores of all the algorithms for training and testing data.

Figure 2: Accuracy of all algorithms for Train and Test data

For training data, in terms of accuracy, Decision Tree got highest 100% accuracy. The performance of Decision Tree was followed by Linear SVC with 99% accuracy, Random Forest with 98% accuracy and KNN with 88% accuracy.

For testing data, in terms of accuracy Decision Tree got highest 94% accuracy, while Linear SVC got 92%, KNN got 88% and Random Forest got 90% accuracy

Table 3 shows the time required to train our data with the classification models. We can see that KNN was the fastest model to be trained.

Table 4: Training Time of data

Algorithm	Time
Decision Tree	0.175345
Linear SVC	0.008002
KNN	0.000000
Random Forest	0.032013

Table 4 shows the prediction time required for each classification model. In this case, Linear SVC was the fastest to predict.

Table 5: Prediction Time of data

Algorithm	Time
Decision Tree	0.007999
Linear SVC	0.000000
KNN	0.071975
Random Forest	0.007984

Figure 3: Roc Curves of all ML algorithms

Figure 3 depicts the roc curves of all the algorithms. From figure 2, it is clear that Decision tree has the highest roc area (0.77). The second highest roc area is obtained by Random Forest (0.65). The other two algorithms, Linear SVC and KNN obtained 0.62 and 0.61 respectively. Hence it is now clear that Decision Tree is the highest performing algorithm.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study worked with the Bangla texts extracted from image data which are collected from Facebook. Our dataset have 1003 data and TF-IDF is used for feature extraction before training. We evaluated our model using Decision Tree, Linear SVC, KNN and Random Forest classifier. Our research showed that, Decision Tree performed best among all the algorithms for our dataset. Since our dataset is an imbalanced dataset, f1-score is an important metrics for our model. We achieved 75% f1-score and 94% accuracy using Decision Tree classifier. As our dataset is small compared to other dataset, the results might differ for larger dataset. We will try to work with a larger dataset in future and add more features. We hope that our findings will be useful to the research community in conducting future studies in this area.

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